

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

HISTORICAL AND DEMOGRAPHIC ISSUES RELATED TO ANCIENT BELIEFS, CUSTOMS AND CEREMONIES OF THE AZERBAIJANI PEOPLE (ON THE BASIS OF AZERBAIJANI HISTORIOGRAPHY IN SECOND HALF OF THE XX - EARLY XXI CENTURIES)

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Abstract

The Azerbaijani people are one of the most ancient peoples of the world. In Azerbaijan, even in antiquity there was a great propensity for large families. Many rites of Azerbaijan contain rich demographic elements. In Azerbaijan, some of these customs still exist. For example: during childbirth, near the bride were midwives, mother of a daughter-in-law, and an older sister. After giving birth, the daughter-in-law was given sherbet, the girl's navel was buried on the doorstep in the corner of the room, and the boy's navel was buried in a mosque or in a stall. Until the end of 40 days, did not allow strangers to the child. These customs gave impetus to the increase in the number of marriages. People, the newlyweds knew each other before the wedding so the families were strong and the number of fertility was a lot.

Keywords: historical demography, Azerbaijan traditions and customs, ancient beliefs of the Azerbaijan people, the cult of the Sun, Azerbaijani historiography.

It is possible to find numerous valuable and interesting information about historical and demographic issues (such as growth and birth) in the ancient beliefs of the Azerbaijani people. According to the oldest beliefs of the Azerbaijani people, everything that is alive must grow, reproduce, take root like a tree, and branch out like tree branches. It is no coincidence that Azerbaijani people has a word of blessing: "I want that you to have a thousand branches like a tree". In this word of blessing, the worship of the tree of life, which is one of our ancient beliefs, is reflected. In many Turkic-speaking peoples, including other peoples, the goddess of birth and fertility is identified with a tree, and often with a plentiful tree, or is depicted as a double tree. For example, one of the seals found from the Sumerian city-state of Uruk depicts Inanna, the goddess of birth and fertility, holding the tree of life. So, since the most ancient times, people have imagined plentiful trees in a closely related manner related to demographic processes such as growth and reproduction.

M. Mathieu notes that in many ancient mythological belief systems, the creation of the sky and the universe is associated with a tree. According to one of these beliefs, the child of the Sun, that was once in darkness, was formed in the petals of a lotus towering on a high elevation. This is how the lotus that grew on the hill near the city of Shmunu gave life to the young Sun Goddess. The description of the lotus flower, with the holy child sitting among its petals, is found in the legends of the Roman period [11, p.15-16]. In this example, the "coming out" of the plant and the sun as the parents of the "holy child" actually proves once again that people associate growth and population settlement only with natural favorable factors. That is, from the earliest times, our great ancestors understood that wood, sun, air, water, and soil are important components for normal living, reproduction, and generation on earth, and they valued the absence of any of these

factors as the end of life. The tree of life, which is a symbol of life and growth on earth, was seen as a unity of these four sacred elements: "In ancient Azerbaijan, the tree of life was known as a symbol of the noblest and highest ideals of Azerbaijani people, as a sign of immortality and eternal life. The connection between the tree of life imaginations and the sun symbol has traditionally been passed down from generation to generation" [14, p.54-55].

The depiction of the goddess protecting birth and growth together with a tree on the artistic embroidery attributed to the Altai Turks in the Hermitage museum confirms the above once again. The image on that art sample, which belongs to the IV-III centuries, clearly shows that the ancient Turkic-speaking peoples treated the tree of life as the protector of birth. According to M. Seyidov: "The "world tree" is considered the creator and protector of the whole world, as well as people. If such a belief prevailed, then Umay, the goddess who protects children with a tree, should naturally be associated with a tree" [13, p.37]. A number of Turkic-speaking peoples believed that the tree of life descended from the sky together with Umay, the goddess who protects birth and children. The association of Umay, the goddess of birth, with the plentiful tree was due to the fact that both were directly related to growth and reproduction, as mentioned above. That is, if the tree bears fruit and grows, the goddess Umay also helps the birth of people, which ensures the increase of generations; she patronized pregnant women and their children.

The traditions, customs and rituals of the Azerbaijani people are distinguished by their primacy, completeness of content and thematic extensiveness among the national cultures of the peoples of the world. These customs and rituals were formed as a result of the centuries-old history of cohabitation of the Turkic peoples.

Many of them reflect the beauty characteristic of ancient times. From this point of view, the rituals associated with the worship of the Sun, folk beliefs are of great interest. The cult of the Sun or worship of the Sun, which is one of the ancient traditions of Azerbaijan, retaining its incarnation in the customs of Nowruz, could be preserved from the ancient times of our ancestors to the present day in one form or another. Sun plays a decisive role for the existence of life, development, progress and improvement on our planet [10, p.209]. Our morning begins with the first rays of the sun peeking over the horizon, and everyone starts their working day. In the early stages of human existence, there was no artificial light. People used only Sunlight and Moonlight, and in their absence they found themselves in complete darkness. Therefore, our ancestors worshiped the Sun and the Moon [1, p.44].

In honor of the sun, a sacrifice was made. According to the "father of history" Herodotus, the Massagetae tribes living in the modern territory of Azerbaijan considered the sun to be the only God and sacrificed a tree to a horse [6, p.234; 4, p.478]. Azerbaijani historians K.Aliyev and F.Aliyeva wrote: "Some ancient tribes living in the modern territory of Azerbaijan considered the long-lived oak as a symbol of population growth and prosperity and brought this tree as a horse sacrifice, they splashed the bark of this tree with the blood of a killed horse" [3, p. 63]. According to the ancient astral view of the Azerbaijani people, the horse and the bull were considered a symbol of the sun, as well as a symbol of prosperity and population growth. The sacrifice of a horse to the sun, as well as the frequent images of a bull in the rocks of Gobustan, confirm the connection between the sun and the Earth [5, p.214; 4, p.478].

Thus, the cult of the Sun originated as a result of the need of our ancestors for light and warmth, their attitude to the environment, and over the course of millennia, it influenced the development of man and the formation of sacred thinking. Then our ancestors, in order to bring themselves closer to the sun, to become a relative with it, created images that included mythical creatures, created images, the status of the sun as a document of sacredness. One such being was "Al Ruh" (literally – "red spirit"), that fought against the forces of darkness, the enemies of slander. Belief in "Al Ruh" is still preserved in some areas of Azerbaijan, customs and traditions. When the sun and moon were darkened, people united their efforts and helped the sun. Regarding this, N.Rzayev writes: "In Azerbaijan at the end of the XIX and beginning of the XX centuries, Al Ruh was opposed to evil spirits as a good spirit. When the sun and moon were eclipsed, they called him for help. In the beginning, fires were lit, salutes and guns were fired, and drums were beaten so that the sun or moon would get rid of evil spirits" [12, p.42; 7, p.164].

In the ancient beliefs of the Azerbaijani people, there was the image of Humay, who protected pregnant women, newborn children, the family hearth from any evil spirits, and also patronized the growth of the pop-

ulation. Most likely, these female images were associated with the period of matriarchy, when the genus was considered on the maternal side. Later, these female images patronizing the population were associated with the cult of the sun. Yellow and red color in the ancient beliefs of the Azerbaijani people personified the fire of the patronizing sun. That is why, both Albasti and Humay were depicted as a virtuous woman with golden yellow, red braids. Therefore our ancient ancestors took care of their future children and held a series of rituals and measures to protect pregnant women from the negative effects of evil spirits. For example, pregnant women's blankets and head coverings were made of red cloth.

Thus, the wealth of ancient beliefs, customs and rituals of the Azerbaijani people related to family values, caring for pregnant women and newborn children, population growth is indisputable evidence of the richness and antiquity of the demographic views of our people, which have made a valuable contribution to human civilization.

References

1. Ahmedov Q. How we have reached our days. Baku, "Azernesh", 1989, 115 p.
2. Aliyarli S. Issues of Azerbaijan philology. Baku, "Elm", 1984, 264 p.
3. Aliyev K., Aliyeva F. Azerbaijan in ancient period. Baku, "Azerneshr", 1997, 120 p.
4. Azerbaijani ethnography in 3 volumes. Vol.3. Baku, "Qerb-Sherq", 2007, 568 p.
5. Farajova M. Rock art of Azerbaijan. Baku, "Aspoligraf", 2009, 384 p.
6. Herodotus. History. Baku, "Azerneshr", 1998, 329 p. 234;
7. Klengel-Brandt E. Journey to ancient Babylon. Moscow, "Nauka", 1979, 259 p.
8. Mammadov A. Beliefs of our people about Nowruz holiday. History and its problems, No. 2, 2016. pp. 327-331.
9. Mammadov A. Demographic views on the ancient beliefs, customs and ceremonies of the Azerbaijani people. History and its problems, No. 1, 2018, pp. 344-349.
10. Mammadov A. The cult of the Sun in the pre-Islamic system of beliefs of the Azerbaijani people. Akademik Tarih ve Düşünce Dergisi, Uluslararası Hakemi Dergi Cilt:IV/sayı:XI/Mayıs/MMXVII, Ankara Universiteti, 2017, p.207-216.
11. Mathieu M.E. Ancient Egyptian myths. Moscow-Leningrad, "Publishing house of the ANSSR", 1956.
12. Rzayev N. The voice of centuries. Baku, "Azerneshr", 1974, 80 p.
13. Seyidov M. The sources of Azerbaijan mythological thought. Baku, "Yazichi", 1983, 326 p.
14. Tahmasib M. Azerbaijani oral folk literature until the 7th century. History of Azerbaijani literature, vol. 1. Baku, 1960.